

Exploring nucleon-induced reactions on Selenium-80 using COMPLET code

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Abstract

The variation of nuclear reaction cross-sections with the variation in projectile energies is called excitation functions has been a subject of great interest since last few decades. They beautifully display the pre-equilibrium as well as equilibrium emission of particles. Nucleon-induced reactions on medium-mass nuclei are important for nuclear-structure studies and isotope production. Selenium-80 is a target for producing bromine, arsenic, and germanium isotopes. The aim of this study is to compute and validate cross sections for key proton- and neutron-induced reactions on ⁸⁰Se that produce ^{76,77}Br, ⁷⁶As, ⁷⁷Ge, and ⁸⁰As. Excitation functions for ⁸⁰Se(p, 4n)⁷⁷Br, ⁸⁰Se(p, 5n)⁷⁶Br, ⁸⁰Se(p, α)⁷⁶As, ⁸⁰Se(n, α)⁷⁷Ge, and ⁸⁰Se(n, p)⁸⁰As were calculated with the COMPLET code and compared to literature data. COMPLET reproduces the main features of the measured excitation functions, matching peak energies and magnitudes for most channels. The results of such calculations were compared to predictions of a well-established optical potential and with experimental data, reaching very good agreement. COMPLET reliably models the investigated reactions on ⁸⁰Se and yields cross sections useful for isotope production and reaction studies. The results aid beam-energy selection and experimental planning for producing ^{76,77}Br, ⁷⁶As, ⁷⁷Ge, and ⁸⁰As and support further model refinement.

Keywords

Excitation function, Level density, Equilibrium, Pre-equilibrium, EXFOR

Introduction

A nuclear reaction is initiated when a nucleon or nucleus collides with another nucleon or nucleus. Reactions are characterized in first place by the incoming nuclei and the outgoing reaction products. A complete description of a nuclear reaction involves other observable quantities beside the incoming nuclei and the outgoing reaction products. The study of nuclear reactions is a crucial field of study for comprehending nuclear physics (Cerutti et al. 2019). A nuclear reaction occurs when a high-speed projectile strikes a target nucleus, changing the target nucleus's energy and composition in the process (Griswold 2016).

Nuclear reactors of many kinds, including cyclotrons and accelerators, create radionuclides of interest. The physical basis of radionuclide generation can be improved by using the data gathered from these procedures (Al-Abyad 2012).

Therefore, understanding these processes and precisely measuring and computing the cross section of nuclear reactions are essential (Tadesse 2007). Plotting $\sigma(E)$ against E yields the excitation function (ExF) (Reimer 2022). Proton and neutron-induced nuclear reactions on the selenium-80 isotope are essential for nuclear technology, dosimeter use, radioactive waste management, and the creation of medicinal radioisotopes (Noori et al. 2018).

Comprehensive knowledge of the excitation radioisotope produced in order to lower radioactive impurities and increase the yield of the targeted product. Selenium was our preferred target isotope for the study of nucleon-induced nuclear reactions because of its function as a building block in nuclear technology, a target material in the development of weapons, and the creation of medicinal radionuclide production used for therapeutic purposes. Also, in its natural composition, selenium consists of thirty-one isotopes (from $A = 64$ – 94 have been discovered so far) these include 6 stable, 11 proton-rich and 14 neutron-rich isotopes (Claes et al. 2010). Thus, off which Se-80 is the most stable isotopes and choice as a target isotope for this induced reaction.

Code developers can immediately improve predictions for other nuclides for which there is no experimental data by reducing calculation uncertainties if reaction cross-sections for both neutrons and protons (13.5 to 70.5 MeV) as well as a full set of (p, xn), (p, α), (n, xn), and (n, xp) cross sections are available. Both theoretical and experimental methods require nuclear data for several target elements across a broad range of energies (Angdasaw 2013). Cross-sections of particle-induced reactions are often estimated using nuclear reaction models, especially when experimental data is either unavailable or unsuitable because of experimental problems (Kaplan et al. 2009). Various stastically applicable nuclear codes such as COMPLET, TALYS 1.96 (1.95), and EMPIRE 3.2 for the given projectile energy were applicable for the theoretical reaction cross-section calculations (Petrosyan 2025; Mekonen and Rao 2025; Mekonen and Rao 2023).

By integrating equilibrium and pre-equilibrium methods with experimental data from the EXFOR database, the computer code COMPLET has enabled theoretical analysis of the statistics (data) under the calculations based exclusively on hybrid and geometry-dependent hybrid models (Mekonen and Mekonen 2023). Pearson's correlation coefficient is used to compare theory and experiment. A range of equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction models are described in this study. There has been insufficient experimental and theoretical comparison of excitation functions caused by protons and neutrons on the ^{80}Se isotope (do Carmo and Alves 2022). By employing the computer method COMPLET and the EXFOR database to assess the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section processes of nucleon-induced nuclear reactions on the Selenium-80 isotope from 13.5 to 70.5 MeV projectile energies, this work closes this knowledge gap. Investigating nucleon-induced reactions on Selenium-80 isotopes is the main goal of this effort, with an emphasis on comprehending the reaction mechanisms and using simulation to determine crucial nuclear parameters.

Methodology

Evaluation of nuclear data is based on experimental data and theoretical computational models (Werdofa 2012). It is neither practical nor economically difficult to measure

the required cross-sections of all isotopes in the periodic table over a wide range of energies. A nuclear reaction model is always required to obtain cross-section estimates for particle-induced reactions (Asres et al. 2019a). This reaction model is of great importance when experimental data are not available or the cross-section cannot be measured due to experimental difficulties. Therefore, a nuclear reaction cross-section calculation plays an important role in nuclear data analysis.

Experimental data sources

The experimental reaction cross-section data and the corresponding projectile energy data were generated from the experimental nuclear reaction data base (EXFOR), which has recently stored experimental measurements of reaction cross sections for alpha particles, protons, neutrons, deuterons, and etc; the reader is referred to these reports for additional experimental details.

EXFOR data center

EXFOR, the library and format for collecting, exchanging, and preserving experimental nuclear reaction data, is maintained by the IAEA's Nuclear Data Department (NDS) (Asres et al. 2019b). Data from experimental nuclear processes can be collected, stored, shared, and retrieved using this format and library (Kara 2017). The product nuclei differ in terms of particle energy, half-lives, and other properties.

Computer code COMPLET

In this study the COMPLET nuclear reaction code were employed for the calculation of excitation function for the nucleon induced reaction on stable selenium-80 isotope. Nucleon-cross sections on a range of isotopes have been predicted using theoretical reaction codes such as COMPLET, which are based on various nuclear theories. The computer code COMPLET was developed using the Weisskopf-Ewing model, which describes the equilibrium process before particle emission, and Blann's Hybrid model, which takes into account the shape and configuration of the interacting nuclei for both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium processes (Yigit 2020). The COMPLET is computer software, which is developed using FORTRAN programming language, and can calculates nuclear reactions cross-section and also as used by different scholars for the calculation of excitation function for compound and pre-compound nuclear reaction for air induced reaction mechanisms the (Zegeye et al. 2025; Mekonen and Rao 2025; Degu Belete et al. 2024; Asres et al. 2019a). The method used in this work is an important and typical calculation method and also results were compared with the existing experimental results to verify calculation method. The findings of the model excitation function data were validated against experimental excitation function data, which were retrieved from the EXFOR data centre.

Computer code COMPLET formalism and input parameters

The initial excitation configurations and level density parameters are crucial variables in pre-equilibrium emission calculations. Various input parameters were used in the complete code to estimate reactions (Yiğit 2020). Pre-equilibrium emission calculations heavily rely on the level density parameters and initial excitation configurations. The Complete code estimated reactions using a variety of input parameters. The calculated excitation functions' shape and height are influenced by the nuclear level density. When the decay rate equation governing nuclear transformation and decay of the activated products is taken into account, the expression for nuclear reaction cross-section can be written (Ditrói et al. 2018). By using the Fermi density distribution function as shown in Equation (1):

$$\rho(E) = \frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{2\sqrt{aE}}}{12a^{\frac{1}{4}} E^{\frac{5}{4}}} \quad (1)$$

Where a , is the level density parameter and E is the excitation energy. The level density parameter, which was determined through experiment, exhibits a linear relationship with the mass number of the compound nucleus expressed as in Equation (2):

$$a = \frac{A_{CN}}{K} \quad (2)$$

Where A_{CN} stands for the compound nucleus's mass number and K for the free adjustable constant ranging from 7 to 12. Theoretical calculations in this work were done by using the level density parameter with the application of free adjustable constant K from 7 to 12, for all the reactions. However, using free adjustable constants of

11 and 12 in Equation (1) (i.e., $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{11}$, and $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{12}$)

are the best fit to experimental results for proton induced

and k is equal to 8 and 7 (i.e., $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{8}$ and $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{7}$)

are best fit to experimental results for neutron induced reaction. Also exciton number $n_0 = 1$ and $n_0 = 3(2p+h)$ are used but $n_0 = 2, 3, 4$ and 5 are found to give satisfactory reproduction of the experimental data for both reactions.

These excitons interact independently with the particles below the Fermi level, creating new particle-hole configuration in the second stage or getting emitted into the continuum (Barbaro et al. 2021). The input parameters incorporated in the code COMPLET in this work for the given projectile energy for the theoretically calculated

pre-equilibrium and equilibrium reaction mechanism are selected and considered based on the recently existed literatures of (Asres et al. 2019b; Degu Belete et al. 2024; Mekonen and Rao 2025; Zegeye et al. 2025).

Correction to the raw data

The uncorrected reaction cross section, (σ_{un}) , was derived for every forward cone size from, shown in Equation (3):

$$\sigma_{un} = \frac{1}{nx} \left[\frac{(I_0 - I)}{I_0} - \frac{(i_0 - i)}{i_0} \right] \quad (3)$$

where x is the target thickness and n is the number of nuclei per unit volume in the target. For every target, a set of target-in and target-out measurements were made. The difference between the term $(I_0 - I)$ and the corresponding quantity $(i_0 - i)$ derived from target-out measurements was used to calculate the uncorrected reaction cross section (σ_{un}) .

Data analysis and comparison

The data for this work was properly organized by tabulating and presenting the results using a spread sheet. Theoretical and experimental response profiles plotted against projectile energy using Origin-2018 software. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R-value) was used to assess the relationship between the experimental and theoretical total cross-section values and it tells the relationship between the theoretical and experimental results (Asres et al. 2018; Mekonen and Rao 2025).

$$R = \frac{\sum_i^N ((XT_i - \langle XT \rangle)(XE_i - \langle XE \rangle))}{N - 1 (S_{XT})(S_{XE})} \quad (4)$$

where R - stands for the correlation coefficient having the values lies between 1 and -1 and unit less, S_{XT} and S_{XE} for the standard deviations of the theoretical and experimental cross-sections, and N for the quantity of theoretical and experimental data. These are the mean theoretical and experimental cross-sections of the i^{th} values, respectively (Asres et al. 2018). According to (Mekonen and Rao 2025), the values of person correlation coefficient have five range values to show the relationship between experimental results with theoretical results. When the values of $R > 0.9$ indicates an excellent correlation; the values $0.7 < R \leq 0.9$ indicates a strong correlation; $0.5 < R \leq 0.7$ indicates a moderate correlation; $0.3 < R \leq 0.5$ indicates a weak correlation; $R \leq 0.3$ indicates a very weak or no correlation.

Calculations and analysis of errors

The percentage (%) error can be obtained using this formula as shown in Equation (5):

$$\text{Percent error} = \left| \frac{\text{experimental value} - \text{theoretical value}}{\text{theoretical value}} \right| \% \quad (5)$$

In research, significant numbers are important, and even if the question is posed correctly, presenting an

answer that is either excessively or insufficiently expenditure may be considered erroneous (Helmenstine 2020).

In this work, the excitation functions for an induced reaction of proton $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ and an induced reaction of neutron $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$ and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ were calculated using computer code COMPLET with possible input parameters.

Results and discussions

To gain a deeper understanding of the experimental results, cross-section prediction utilizing nuclear reaction codes is crucial (Yigit 2020). Excitation functions for nucleon-mediated reactions are important for many medical applications and for the development of advanced nuclear reaction theory (Noori et al. 2018). In this work we have been investigated computationally to find theoretical excitation functions for the production of radionuclide isotopes using proton- and neutron-induced nuclear reactions on selenium-80 isotopes.

The new calculations on the excitation functions of five reactions channels were studied under this work. These are: $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ are proton induced whereas regarding neutrons induced $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ are carried out in the 10 MeV to 70 MeV incident energy range using computer code COMPLET for theoretical calculation. The COMPLET code gives the results of both the equilibrium reaction and the pre-equilibrium reaction. The experimental cross section data for nucleon-induced reaction on selenium-80 isotope in the above projectile energy ranges were obtained from the EXFOR data source (Otuka et al. 2014).

Table 1 also displays the half-life and decay data of the radioisotopes created in this study. The theoretical and experimental cross-sections are plotted against the projectile energy are shown in Fig. 1 to Fig. 5. The projectile energy is measured in Mega electro Volt (MeV) and the cross-section is measured in mill barn (mb). The experimental data for the reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$ and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$ are taken from the Author of (Spahn et al. 2019) in EXFOR data center. And the data for $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ taken from the Author (Levkovski 2019) in EXFOR data center. And the experimental data regarding neutron the data for the reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$ and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ is taken from the Author (Filatenkov 2021) and (Decowski et al. 2021), respectively in EXFOR data center. Also energy range selected from the data is same with theoretical. This makes easy for comparison. The cross-section of theoretical and experimental with the energy range is given in Table 2 to Table 6.

Table 1. Q-value and decay information for the product radioisotopes

Reaction channels	Reaction product	Half-life	Mode of decay	Q-value in MeV
$^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$	^{77}Br	57.036 h	EC(100%)	1.4
$^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$	^{76}Br	16.2 h	EC(57%), $\text{B}^+(43)\%$	5.0
$^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$	^{76}As	1 d	$\text{B}^-(100\%)$	3.0
$^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$	^{77}Ge	11 h	$\text{B}^-(100\%)$	2.7
$^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$	^{80}As	9.01 m	$\text{B}^-(100\%)$	2.3

Decay data and Q-values for products of $^{80}\text{Se}(p, x)$ and (n, x) reactions

The table summarizes Q-values and decay data for several product radioisotopes produced from reactions on a selenium-80 target. For the $(p, 4n)$ channel producing ^{77}Br , the product has a half-life of 57.0 hours and decays purely by electron capture (EC), with a Q-value of 1.4 MeV. The $(p, 5n)$ channel yields ^{76}Br , which has a 16.2 hour half-life and decays by a mixture of electron capture (57%) and positron emission (β^+ , 43%), and its Q-value is 5.0 MeV. Proton-induced alpha emission (p, α) produces ^{76}As , a nuclide with a 1.0 day half-life that decays exclusively by beta-minus emission (β^-) and has a Q-value of 3.0 MeV. Neutron-induced alpha emission (n, α) leads to ^{77}Ge , which has an 11 hour half-life, decays 100% by beta-minus, and has a Q-value of 2.7 MeV. Finally, the (n, p) reaction produces ^{80}As with a short half-life of 9.0 minutes, decaying entirely by beta-minus and having a Q-value of 2.3 MeV.

The proton induced reactions

In this study, the excitation functions for protons induced for $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ reactions were obtained using COMPLET computer code and the results are plotted in Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 at proton energies up to 70.5 MeV. The calculations results are compared with experimental values from EXFOR library.

In general, the nuclear reactions $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ are employed to produced ^{77}Br , ^{76}Br and ^{76}As respectively. The theoretical calculations are in agreement with the experimental data, as shown in Fig. 1, with the expectation of one experimental value in the peaked region, which is approximately 30% higher. As seen in Fig. 3 the experimental data the peaked region is approximately 25% lower. As noted for proton induced $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ reactions, the best energy range for production is from 34.5 to 43.4 MeV, 53.9 to 61.4 MeV and from 24.8 to 28.5 MeV, respectively.

Bromine-77 Radioisotope Production (^{77}Br)

Several isotopes of bromine have long been proposed for use in nuclear medicine. Bromine-77 has a half-life of 57 hours and decays almost completely (99.3%) by capturing electrons. Its half-life is suitable for long-term physiological studies using single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) (Mohamed and Shehata 2011). In addition, the Auger electrons emitted during the decay of Bromine-77 have certain therapeutic implications. Several methods have been proposed for obtaining the radionuclides under consideration. However, the proton-mediated reaction on selenium appears to be the most important (Mohamed and Shehata 2011). Bromine-77 occurs when a projectile (proton particle) hits the target element selenium-80 and emits four neutrons (4n). By comparing the calculated values with the experimental results, the pre-equilibrated and the equilibrated reactions can be seen in the reaction excitation function $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$.

Table 2. Theoretical evaluation of $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$ reaction cross-section computed with experimental data

ExEn (MeV)	$\sigma(\text{Exp})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{Pre-EQ})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{EQ})$ (mb)
34.5±0.4	20.0±2.0	20.7±0.03	27.4±0.20
37.4±0.3	98.0±11.0	99.81±0.02	140.6±0.30
40.6±0.5	214.0±23.0	202.6±0.06	308.7±0.30
43.4±0.5	231.0±25.0	265.2±0.12	430.3±0.46
46.2±0.4	189.0±21.0	211.1±0.10	494.3±0.61
48.8±0.3	216.0±24.0	257.6±0.16	471.5±0.54
51.3±0.3	160.0±17.0	210.3±0.23	406.6±0.60
53.9±0.3	174.0±19.0	174.0±0.00	356.0±0.51
56.5±0.3	122.0±13.0	117.1±0.04	250.9±0.51
59.0±0.2	73.0±8.0	92.5±0.20	207.6±0.64
60.3±0.3	31.0±3.0	65.1±0.52	146.9±0.79
61.4±0.2	90.0±10.0	55.2±0.62	126.9±0.30
62.4±0.2	81.0±9.0	47.3±0.71	109.7±0.26
63.7±0.2	46.0±5.0	39.0±0.18	91.8±0.50
64.4±0.2	91.0±10.0	34.0±1.67	80.0±0.13
66.0±0.2	49.0±5.0	30.2±0.62	74.2±0.33
66.5±0.4	73.0±8.0	23.6±2.0	56.4±0.30
68.5±0.4	51.0±6.0	16.7±2.09	39.7±0.28

Figure 1. Excitation functions for proton reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$.

The experimental data for this reaction are taken from the author (Spahn et al. 2019).

As shown in Fig. 1, the excitation function for the reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$ was experimentally measured and theoretically calculated using different sets of input parameters. The pre-equilibrium reaction cross-sections reach its maximum peak at 155.5 mb while equilibrium reaction cross-section attains its maximum peak value at 494.3 mb. At high energies, the theoretical pre-equilibrium cross-section agrees with the experimental results reported by (Spahn et al. 2019) in EXFOR. The compound nucleus theory is not valid for a larger number of neutron emissions, as its value is much larger than the experimental value.

So, the equilibrium reaction gives the best results up to 46.2 MeV with a cross-section value of 430.3 mb. The theoretical pre-equilibrium and equilibrium cross-sections are in good agreement with the experimental data between the energy 34.5 MeV and 43.4 MeV. However, after an incident energy of 43.4 MeV and above, the pre-equilibri-

um reaction cross-section gives better agreement with the experimental data reported by (Spahn et al. 2019) in EXFOR. At higher energies, the equilibrated reaction showed no nuclear emission recombination, and the pre-equilibrated emission gave better results up to 62.4 MeV with the cross-section value 155.5 mb. However, at higher energies above 62.4 MeV, both the pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction mechanisms are far from the experimental values. This confirms that pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction mechanisms are not formed. But it could be a direct reaction mechanism.

Based on the correlation values ($R = 0.945$) between experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section results both have excellent correlations and significant large positive relationship between them. The highest value of person correlation value indicates the predictive capabilities of the model COMPLET for this reaction channel. Whereas, the correlation coefficient between the experimental and the compound nuclear reactions cross section is to be ($R = 0.892$) and we said that there is strong positive correlation between them.

It is clear that the theoretical results obtained using the computer code COMPLET are in good agreement with the experimental results obtained from the EXFOR data for energy values up to 66 MeV. Basically, theoretical result has been calculated by using different sets of input parameters, exciton number $n_0 = 5$, level density param-

eter $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{12}$ and mean free path multiplier $MFP = 2$.

This plays a key role in the theoretical calculation for the code COMPLET.

Bromine-76 Radioisotope Production (^{76}Br)

The radioisotope ^{76}Br and ^{77}Br were produced in high radionuclides purity via the proton and neutron irradiation of novel isotopically-enriched, ^{80}Se intermetallic target. Radionuclide Bromine-76 can be used for functional studies with positron emission tomography (PET), the former for fast metabolic processes and the latter for slower processes. Bromine-76 decays by positron emission (58%) and electron capture (42%) (Ellison et al. 2019).

The half-life (16.2 hours) allows the use of radiotracers with an accumulation time of one or two days. The high energy of the emitted positrons can affect the positron emission picture to some extent. Recently, bromine isotopes have received increased attention in the development of PET and high-energy gamma-ray cameras (Mohamed and Shehata 2011). Bromine-76 is produced when a projectile (proton particle) strikes a target element selenium-80 and emits five neutrons (5n). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, is compared with the experimental result taken from the author (Spahn et al. 2019).

As we can see from Table 3 and Fig. 2, both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reactions are possible in the incident energy range of 46.2 MeV to 53.9 MeV. In the

Table 3. Theoretical evaluation of $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$ reaction cross-section computed with experimental data

Exp En(MeV)	$\sigma(\text{Exp})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{Pre-EQ})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{EQ})$ (mb)
46.2±0.4	5.4±0.5	4.4±0.2	6.09±0.7
48.8±0.3	13.0±1.2	10.4±0.2	15.1±0.1
51.3±0.3	20.03±1.8	42.4±0.5	71.19±0.7
53.9±0.3	49.0±4.4	56.4±0.1	101.3±0.5
56.5±0.3	56.9±5.1	93.1±0.4	186.2±0.7
58.9±0.2	49.2±4.4	93.2±0.5	197.9±0.7
61.4±0.2	73.1±6.6	110.0±0.3	252.7±0.7
66.5±0.4	73.3±6.6	88.6±0.2	234.1±0.7
68.5±0.4	50.9±4.6	75.7±0.3	210.6±0.7
70.5±0.4	55.9±5.0	68.0±0.2	186.2±0.7

Figure 2. Excitation functions for proton reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$.

reaction channel of $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$ for the incident energy greater than 53.9 MeV, calculated values of equilibrium reaction are much larger than the experimental value. Radioisotope, bromine-76 is not produced by equilibrium reactions followed by evaporation of five neutrons due to high neutron emission.

The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of experimental and the equilibrium nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($R=0.81$) this indicate a strong correlation between them. Therefore, in the incident energy greater than 53.9 MeV of the $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$ reaction there is a great difference between the excitation functions of the experimental result and the equilibrium nuclear reaction. The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of experimental and pre- equilibrium nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($R=0.93$) for the higher energy region and the result indicated that there is significant large positive and excellent correlation between them. Also, the highest R value confirms the predictive power of the code COMPLET as confirmed by other studies (Mekonen and Rao 2025). Above the incident energy of 56.5 MeV, the pre-equilibrium reaction mechanism better agrees with the experimental data reported by (Spahn et al. 2019) in EXFOR than the pure equilibrium reaction mechanism above 56.5 MeV energy range and there is no signatures of equilibrium reaction. It is clearly observed that for larger numbers of neutron emission the reaction is taking place by pre-equilibrium decay even at the low energy end side.

As a result, the theoretical pre-equilibrium result obtained by using a computer code COMPLET best agrees with the experimental result obtained from the EXFOR data. Basically, theoretical result has been calculated by using different set of input parameters, exciton number

$no = 4$, level density parameter $a = \frac{A_{CN}}{11}$ and mean free

path multiplier $MFP=2$. This plays a key role in the theoretical calculation.

Arsenic-76 radioisotope production (^{76}As)

Arsenic has numerous radionuclides of interest for scientific (medical) or environmental applications. Its chemical properties are similar to those of nitrogen and phosphorus, both of which are common biologically active molecules (Mohamed and Shehata 2011). Arsenic-76, is produced when a projectile (proton particle) strikes a target element selenium-80 and emits (α) particles. Arsenic-76 -decays by negatron emission or undergoes beta minus decay with a 24 hour half-life (Ali et al. 2020). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ is compared with the experimental result taken from the author (Levkovski 2019).

As can be seen from Fig. 3, the experimental values at energy values around 26.6 MeV are very similar to those

Table 4. Theoretical evaluation of $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$ reaction cross-section computed with experimental data

Exp En (MeV)	$\sigma(\text{Exp})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{Pre-EQ})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{EQ})$ (mb)
18.3	3.7	3.6±0.03	6.4±0.42
19.3	4.5	5.7±0.04	10.1±0.55
20.3	9.0	7.9±0.14	13.8±0.35
21.4	11.0	10.2±0.08	17.9±0.37
22.2	13.0	11.6±0.11	20.7±0.37
23.1	15.0	13.3±0.12	23.9±0.37
24.0	17.0	15.3±0.11	27.4±0.37
24.8	19.0	16.2±0.17	28.3±0.32
25.7	22.0	19.6±0.12	34.2±0.35
26.6	22.0	19.0±0.16	34.4±0.36
27.6	23.0	19.7±0.17	35.2±0.34
28.5	23.0	18.6±0.23	31.0±0.25
29.5	24.0	16.7±0.43	26.5±0.09

Figure 3. Excitation functions for proton reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$.

calculated for both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reactions but are closer to pre-equilibrium nuclear emission. In the incident energy range greater than 26.6 MeV, the value calculated by the equilibrium reaction theory is much larger than the experimental value and decreases rapidly, while the experimental value increases slightly.

The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of experimental and equilibrium nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($R=0.91$) this is an excellent positive correlation between them, which means that high experimental value scores go with high equilibrium value scores. They show that there is less evidence of an equilibrium reaction than pre-equilibrium reaction in this energy range. At the higher energies from 26 to 28.5 MeV, the experimental values are very close to nuclear calculations confirming to the formation of a pre-equilibrium reaction.

The pre-equilibrium reaction cross-sections reach its maximum peak at 19.65 mb while equilibrium reaction cross-section attains its maximum peak value at 35.18 mb. It is evident that both the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section are in good agreement with the experimental values up to the incident energies of 26 MeV. After incident energy of 26 MeV and above, the pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section gives better agreement with the experimental data reported by (Levkovski 2019) in EXFOR. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.98$) between experimental and pre-equilibrium reaction cross section has positive and excellent correlation. Furthermore, it is clear to deduce that from the highest values of R given above for the two cases shows the predicted capability of the model COMPLET what we have been used for this reaction channel.

In general, pre-equilibrium reaction formation theory satisfies the results. Above this energy range, no signatures of equilibrium formation are obtained. The compound nucleus theory is not valid for a larger number of neutron emissions, as its value is much larger than the experimental value.

The neutron induced reactions

The production of ^{80}Se in neutron irradiation of ^{77}Ge and ^{80}As occurs in various reactions such as $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$. The results of computer code COMPLET calculations excitation functions for neutron induced reaction were shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The obtained results were compared with the existing experiment in the EXFOR, and a good agreement was obtained. As can be seen in Fig. 4, there are no experimental results for ^{80}Se beyond the energy of 20 MeV. However, it is clarity seen that the COMPLET computer code can be reliably used to obtained data. For Neutron induced, the best energy range for production is from 13.5 to 14.8 MeV and from 15.1 to 15.5 and 16.5 to 17.9 MeV for $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ reactions, respectively.

Germanium-77 Radioisotope Production (^{77}Ge)

The nuclear reaction, $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$ produces ^{77}Ge , which decays by emission of β^- particles into ^{77}Ge with the half-

Table 5. Theoretical evaluation of $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$ reaction cross-section computed with experimental data

Exp En (MeV)	$\sigma(\text{Exp})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{Pre-EQ})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{EQ})$ (mb)
13.5	2.1	2.3±0.09	3.1±0.33
13.9	2.1	2.6±0.03	3.5±0.3
14.1	2.3	2.4±0.07	3.4±0.33
14.3	2.8	2.8±0.00	3.8±0.28
14.4	2.7	2.8±0.04	3.9±0.3
14.8	3.1	3.0±0.03	4.2±0.26

Figure 4. Excitation functions for neutron reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$.

life of 11 hour (Ali et al. 2020). Germanium-77, is produced when a projectile (neutron particle) strikes a target element selenium-80 and emits alpha particles. Germanium-77 is used in medical, industrial and research applications. The calculated excitation functions of the reaction, $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$, is compared with the experimental result taken from the author (Filatenkov 2021).

As we observed the excitation function for the reaction channel, $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$ in Fig. 4, the predicted pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section starts from the bottom of the designated projectile energy of 13.49 MeV up to projectile energy of 14.81 MeV. The pre-equilibrium and the equilibrium reaction cross-section have similar shape to experimental values reported by (Filatenkov 2021) in EXFOR. But, the pre-equilibrium reaction is closer than the equilibrium reaction cross-section. This demonstrates how response mechanisms change as projectile energy rises.

In cases, the experimental and theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section can have maximum values at the projectile energy of 14.81 MeV with values of 3.1 mb, 4.2 mb, and 3.00 mb, respectively. Also, at the projectile energy of 13.5 MeV, the cross-section values for the experimental and theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium are minimum with the values of 2.1 mb, 3.1 mb, and 2.3 mb, respectively. Both, the pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction mechanisms are closer to the experimental values between the energy range 13.5 MeV and 14.8 MeV.

This confirms that there is formation of both pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction mechanisms with equilibrium cross-section values. It is evident that both the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reac-

tion cross-section are good agreement with the experimental values up to incident energy of 14.8 MeV. The correlation coefficient of the cross section of experimental and pre-equilibrium nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($R = 0.99$) and the correlation coefficient between the experimental and the equilibrium cross section nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($R = 0.99$) results of the Pearson correlation in both cases indicated that there is significant large positive excellent correlation between the theoretical and experimental cross-section values. Also, the code COMPLET model, which we have been used for this reaction channel has highest predictive power since due the highest values of ($R = 0.99$). It is clear that the theoretical result obtained by using a computer code COMPLET agree with the experimental result obtained from the EXFOR data.

Arsenic-79 Radioisotope Production (^{80}As)

Arsenic-80 is produced when a projectile (neutron particle) strikes a target element selenium-80 and emits one proton particle. Arsenic-80 decays by negatron emission or undergoes beta minus decay with a 9 minute half-life (Ali et al. 2020). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction, $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ is compared with the experimental result the experimental data taken from the author (Decowski et al. 2021).

From Fig. 5, the theoretical pre-compound nuclear reaction cross-section starts from the bottom of the assigned projectile energy of 13.36 MeV with 1.197 mb, reached its maximum peak at (15.06 MeV, 20.01 mb) and then it begins to increasing with the value of the projectile energy by making long tail.

Table 6. Theoretical evaluation of $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$ reaction cross-section computed with experimental data

Exp En (MeV)	$\sigma(\text{Exp})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{Pre-EQ})$ (mb)	$\sigma(\text{EQ})$ (mb)
13.4±0.14	3.8±3.0	1.2±2.17	1.9±1.0
14.5±0.11	1.0±3.2	6.5±0.8	11.1±0.9
15.1±0.17	8.4±4.4	20.0±0.6	16.4±0.5
15.4±0.20	7.3±2.4	18.7±0.6	22.9±0.6
15.5±0.19	4.1±9.2	18.1±0.7	29.8±0.9
16.5±0.11	13.2±4.2	43.8±0.7	46.7±0.7
17.3±0.2	35.3±10.6	82.6±0.6	63.9±0.4
17.9±0.15	71.2±13.5	82.1±0.1	72.9±0.0

Figure 5. Excitation functions for neutron reaction $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$.

The equilibrium reaction mechanisms have very small similarity with the experimental values in the given energy ranges. At the lower energies around 15.06 MeV experimental values are good agreement to the compound nucleus reaction with the correlation coefficient of the cross section of experimental and equilibrium nuclear reactions is calculated to be ($r = 0.86$), which describes a strong and positive correlation between the theoretical and experimental reaction cross-sections. Therefore, from the above result, it clearly understood that the result of pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section calculated using computer code COMPLET, are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 17.9 MeV as reported by (Decowski et al. 2021) in EXFOR.

General discussion

It is clearly observed that almost in all the reaction channels for the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction mechanisms the results are compared and consistent with other studies done with similar codes of COMPLET (Asres et al. 2019a; Degu Belete et al. 2024; Mekonen and Rao 2025; Zegeye et al. 2025). Also, we confirmed that form studies using computational codes of TAYLS, EMPIRE, and PHITS Monte Carlo code by authors (Özdoğan et al. 2022; Özdoğan et al. 2023; Üncü et al. 2023; Özdoğan et al. 2024; Ozdogan et al. 2025; Wajid et al. 2026) were compared there theoretical findings with experimental results. Thus in both cases we confirmed that the theoretical findings are agreed with experimental results for using different computational codes. Furthermore, it is evident that the extrapolated results from target-in and target-out measurements are extremely comparable. Therefore, the influence is somewhat underestimated by assuming an isotropic distribution of the reaction products. Generally speaking, this effect decreased as atomic number increased, not on an absolute scale, but rather as a relative correction to the reaction cross sections that were observed. We believe that as energy levels rise, these corrections will also rise.

Despite several experimental sites that deviate greatly from the predictions, the two computations anticipate an acceptable agreement with the experimental energy dependency. Further precise measurements in the energy region 13.5 to 70.5 MeV should undoubtedly provide a significant constraint on future attempts to derive global potentials as well as in the testing of current global potentials. The primary difference between the two predictions is the decrease with energy in the energy region 13.5 to 70.5 MeV.

The strong correlation between our experimental findings and the global potentials' predictions suggests that this specific measurement may not have a significant effect on the global potentials. However, the energy dependences up to 70.5 MeV contain major uncertainties, and we think that the global potentials might be significantly affected by a longer experiment at much energy between 13.5 to 70.5 MeV.

Conclusion

We calculated excitation functions for five reaction channels on $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 4n)^{77}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, 5n)^{76}\text{Br}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(p, \alpha)^{76}\text{As}$, $^{80}\text{Se}(n, \alpha)^{77}\text{Ge}$, and $^{80}\text{Se}(n, p)^{80}\text{As}$, over incident projectile energies from 13.5 to 70.5 MeV using both equilibrium (compound-nucleus) and pre-equilibrium formalisms, then compared the results with experimental cross-sections from EXFOR. With careful selection of nuclear-model parameters, the predicted excitation functions reproduce the main trends and magnitudes of the measured data, particularly for proton-induced reactions in the low-to-medium energy range. Around 13 to 15 MeV, a combined compound-nucleus and pre-compound description gives the best agreement with experiment.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

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The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

The study was developed and designed by TAM, who completed all the work, searched for relevant papers, evaluated and interpreted the data, and wrote the manuscript. YHA supervised, designed, and critically revised the present version of the document. The draft manuscript was designed and with input from SMZ and EYB. The final manuscript was reviewed by the authors, who gave their approval for submission.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.